

THE CENTRAL LIMIT THEOREM AND THE ROLE OF THE NORMAL DISTRIBUTION IN ITS APPLICATION

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Abstract. *This article discusses the mathematical essence of the Central Limit Theorem, the principles of its proof, and its relationship with the normal distribution. The paper analyzes the practical applications of the theorem in economics, engineering, and natural sciences. The importance of the normal distribution in statistical modeling and its role as a universal law in probability theory are highlighted. The research results expand the possibilities of analyzing and predicting real processes using the Central Limit Theorem.*

Keywords: *normal distribution, Central Limit Theorem, probability theory, statistical analysis, modeling.*

Introduction

In the modern era, the role of probability theory is increasingly expanding in statistical modeling, big data, and artificial intelligence systems. One of the central ideas of this theory, the Central Limit Theorem, serves as an important methodological basis for deeply analyzing random processes, generalizing results, and modeling real phenomena. The Central Limit Theorem is a fundamental result that proves that the distribution of the sum of independent random variables with various probability distributions approaches the normal distribution as their number increases. As one of the core concepts of mathematical statistics, this theorem elevates the normal distribution to the level of a “Law of Nature.” Therefore, it is widely applied in analyzing market trends, detecting measurement errors, and estimating population parameters.

In modern analysis processes, the sum of any random variable or statistical data nearly follows a normal distribution. This situation further strengthens the practical significance of the Central Limit Theorem and creates a reliable foundation for statistical models. Consequently, analyzing the theoretical essence of the Central Limit Theorem, determining its applications in practical fields, and scientifically revealing the role of the normal distribution in this process are of great importance. The essence of the theorem is that under certain conditions, the sum of independent and identically distributed random variables with a common distribution approaches a normal distribution.

Central Limit Theorem:

: “ X_1, X_2, \dots, X_n let the random variables be independent, identically distributed, $MX_i = a$ and have finite expected value and, then $DX_i = \sigma^2, i = \overline{1, n}$ finite variance, $0 < \sigma^2 < \infty$ then

$$Z_n = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n X_i - M\left(\sum_{i=1}^n X_i\right)}{\sqrt{D\left(\sum_{i=1}^n X_i\right)}} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n X_i - na}{\sigma\sqrt{n}}$$

the distribution of the standardized random variable converges to the standard normal distribution

$$F_{Z_n}(x) = P\{Z_n < x\} \xrightarrow{n \rightarrow \infty} \Phi(x) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi}} \int_{-\infty}^x e^{-t^2/2} dt$$

as $n \rightarrow \infty$;

Thus, for sufficiently large values of n ,

$$Z_n \square N(0,1), \text{ bo'lib } S_n = X_1 + \dots + X_n$$

and the sum is distributed according to the following normal law:

a:**

$$S_n \square N(na, \sqrt{n}\sigma)$$

In this case $\sum_{i=1}^n X_i$ the random variable is said to be asymptotically normally distributed.

If a random variable X satisfies $MX = 0, DX = 1$ bo'lsa X then the variable X is called a centralized and normalized (or standard) random variable.”

For sufficiently large values of n , it becomes possible to calculate the probabilities of

events related to the sum of random variables. $S_n = \sum_{i=1}^n X_i$ if we standardize the random variable, then for sufficiently large n

$$P\left\{\alpha \leq \sum_{i=1}^n X_i \leq \beta\right\} = P\left\{\frac{\alpha - na}{\sigma\sqrt{n}} \leq \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n X_i - na}{\sigma\sqrt{n}} \leq \frac{\beta - na}{\sigma\sqrt{n}}\right\} \approx \Phi\left(\frac{\beta - na}{\sigma\sqrt{n}}\right) - \Phi\left(\frac{\alpha - na}{\sigma\sqrt{n}}\right),$$

or

$$P\{\alpha \leq S_n \leq \beta\} \approx \Phi\left(\frac{\beta - MS_n}{\sqrt{DS_n}}\right) - \Phi\left(\frac{\alpha - MS_n}{\sqrt{DS_n}}\right), [1].$$

the formula becomes applicable.

The first form of the Central Limit Theorem was introduced by A. de Moivre in 1733 for the binomial distribution. Later, Laplace generalized this result and demonstrated that as the number of random variables increases infinitely, their distribution converges to a stable normal form. K. Gauss applied the normal distribution to error theory. The importance of the Central Limit Theorem lies in the fact that it explains why the results of nearly all natural or social processes tend to take a “normal” form.

The normal distribution is one of the most important and widely occurring distributions in probability theory. It is also commonly referred to as the Gaussian distribution or the law of errors. A unique property of the normal distribution is that it is a limiting distribution, meaning that other distributions converge to it under certain conditions. The normal distribution is the most frequently applied distribution in practice. “An absolutely continuous random variable X is said to be normally distributed if its density function has the following form:

$$f(x) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi}\sigma} e^{-\frac{(x-a)^2}{2\sigma^2}}$$

where: (a) is the mean value; (σ) is the standard deviation; (e) is the base of the natural logarithm.” [1]. In nature and society, many measurements arise from the sum of numerous small, independent random factors. Therefore, the normal distribution is often recognized as a “natural law.” The normal distribution stands at the center of statistical analysis. It is widely used in the following areas:

- **Economics:** stock prices, inflation, risks;
- **Engineering:** measurement errors;
- **Biology:** human height, blood pressure;
- **Pedagogy:** student grades.

The Central Limit Theorem and the normal distribution complement one another. The theorem proves that the sum of any independent random variables approaches the normal distribution. The Central Limit Theorem has practical applications in the following fields:

- **Economic processes:** Many factors have random characteristics. Their sum approaches the normal distribution, which enables risk assessment and financial modeling;
- **Engineering measurements:** Errors accumulate as independent random variables and follow a normal distribution;
- **Biology and medicine:** Human height, blood pressure, and other physiological parameters, being the sum of many factors, approximate a normal distribution;
- **Education:** Test results and student grades behave as random variables that follow the normal distribution, making evaluation and standardization possible.

Conclusion

The normal distribution serves as a fundamental assumption in parametric tests, analysis of variance (ANOVA), and regression models. Furthermore, the normal distribution simplifies various complex systems, making it a reliable tool for forecasting and modeling. Additionally, in big data and artificial intelligence systems, the Central Limit Theorem and the normal distribution provide a foundation for stable algorithm performance, which allows these principles to be applied even more extensively.

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